

Review

Active involvement of students in School

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Abstract

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Active involvement of students in school concerns both the educational procedure and the activities taking place at school, social or otherwise. The study's material consists of articles related to the topic, found in Greek and International $\kappa\alpha\iota$ databases, the Google Scholar, and the Hellenic Academic Libraries (HEAL-Link). Student participation inside school life promotes self-respect and self-confidence. The children start to feel they are being heard, they are valuable and being considered. They also feel more confident in expressing their beliefs in every aspect of their lives and the children that are being encouraged are in a position to develop their own thoughts and gain new skills. Student participation in school, either inside the classroom, or inside the school life in general, provides the children with supplies for their future and experiences, thus making them active citizens.

Keywords: School, Education, Students, Active involvement, School Activities

INTRODUCTION

School prepares students through education and treatment for a productive and successful life, and their unhindered accession in society as a whole after the completion of their post school studies as well (Pappas, 2002). It also prompts kids to take initiatives, equipping them with everything that may be necessary for them, in order to be able to react positively to the challenges of the social environment in which they will stay and operate (Zambeta et al., 2017.)

Active involvement of students in school concerns both the educational procedure and the activities taking place at school, social or otherwise. Student involvement at school can have multiple aspects, going from initially taking place inside the classroom to eventually taking place over the entirety of school life (Avgitidou, 2014). Participation in school life and cooperation with the teachers for the good of the school really should be part of the general learning process, thus giving the students their rights (Avgitidou, 2014; Kaltsas and Gkaintartzi, 2021).

In the reality of everyday education, the learning chances that make active student participation easier are limited (Downer et al., 2007). The tactics that teachers

use are teacher-centered, since the teachers control the learning procedure and teaching time, thus vastly limiting the chances for active involvement (Coodlad, 2004). In this context, the teacher is required to convert the usual teacher-centered tactics, and put the student and the reconstruction of knowledge in the center instead (Sakellariou, et al., 2016).

The purpose of this present study is to present the positive effects that active participation in the learning procedure can have on students. Methods Confused with it and ways for students to achieve it are examined and presented.

The Study consists of a review of Greek and international bibliography. The study's material consists of articles related to the topic found in Greek and international databases such as Google Scholar, the Hellenic Academic Libraries Association (HEAL-Link), and the use of keywords such as school, education, students, active involvement, and activities taking place at school. The exclusion criteria for the articles was the language, except for Greek and English. For the most part, only articles and studies accessible to authors were used.

Active Involvement of Students in the Education Process

Enabling the students to actively participate in the lesson makes the systemization of teaching with the use of pedagogically appropriate strategies necessary. The students do not have many chances to participate, show their preferences and express their opinion (Fredricks and Mccolskey, 2012).

According to the international literature, the answer may be given through the principles of «constructivism». «Constructivism» constitutes a basic learning context related with the active involvement of students. The teacher may guide the students in locating and discovering things themselves, through their enabling, and the relations and connections in between the information they are offered, and expanding their knowledge (Eggen and Kauchak, 2004).

In «constructivism», learning is the result of negotiating, as teacher and students decide what their educational experiences will be like together. (Jacobsen et al, 2009)

These include guided discovery, problem solving, investigation, cooperative learning and discussion. Specifically (Sakellariou and Tsiara, 2017).

- In guided discovery, the teacher provides information to his/her students, so that they will discover a concept that he determines in his aims himself.
- In problem solving, the teacher gives his students the chance to participate in the systematic processing of a problem, which comes true with specific steps, such as spotting the problem and choosing the way it will be solved.
- In investigating, the teacher gives his students the chance to participate in different research processes. The students are being called to make hypotheses, and gather and use information, in order to learn through exporting their own conclusions.
- In cooperative learning, the teacher organizes his students in cooperative teams. The students are working in order to accomplish a common educational goal.
- In discussion, the teacher makes his students take part in a structured discussion-debate, in which each side organizes its arguments. Then, he/she presents it to the entirety of the students, and afterwards, the students' own personal conclusions are produced.

The usage of questions, aimed at both students and teachers, aim to increase interactions inside the classroom, and to motivate as many students as possible (Matsagouras, 2004). In addition, through this process the teacher determines his complementary intervening, while the students regulate their course and behavior as students (Findlay, 2013). As such, teachers can approach students more effectively, pique their interest, and make them actively participate in the educational process (Jacobsen et al., 2009).

Active Participation of Students in School Life

Active involvement in school activities is a right of every student. According to the Ministerial Decision (M.D.) 23/1986/b-619, each student has the same right to participate in school activities, and especially be able to do the following:

- Express their opinion on matters regarding their school lives, their teachers, and the other students of their school.
- Actively interfere in discussions and decision making on matters regarding them, or happening in bodies in which their representatives, that they have elected themselves through collective procedures, participate.
- Responsibly take roles assigned to them.
- Take initiatives that will improve and boost their school life. (Government Gazette 619/B/25-9-1986)

The student's role inside the classroom, as long as he participates, takes a more active form and the student interacts with the learning and life configuring procedures a lot more. (Essex Works, 2003). According to Owens (2009) the extent of children participation in decision-making are related with the following:

- Children can make decisions according to things such as the experiences or activities they wanted, the materials they wanted to use, and the way they wanted to use them.
- Children can participate in the decision-making procedures, and the procedures concerned with solving problems that concern the school in its entirety. Additionally, there are two more types of student participation (Lagos, 2008):
- Pedagogics concerns the student's role and relation with the teachers through an interaction process, with his active involvement both inside the classroom, and throughout the school life in general.
- Administrative is related with the participatory management of the school issues within the context of the cooperation between the teachers and the students, regarding the issues and problems occurring within the school life (Owens, 2009).

Student Benefits from Active Involvement in School

Student participation inside school life promotes self-respect and self-confidence. The children start to feel they are being heard, they are valuable and being considered (Morgan and Streb, 2003). They can also feel more confident in expressing their beliefs in every aspect of their lives and the children that are being encouraged are in a position to develop their own thoughts and gain new skills (Balias, 2011). Decision-making and problem solving through the procedures of communication, exchange of views and feedback are very important skills for Greeks (Thoidis and Haniotakis, 2012).

This way, by actively participating in school activities, the children gain more experiences that will make them capable of judging and evaluating their classmates' opinions and points of view. Mutual respect, mutual understanding and cooperation between students are also developing this way, all of which are very important skills for their further course. (Sakellariou et al., 2016)

In addition, kids feel that they are being listened to and enjoying the appreciation of their classmates and their teachers, through the participation procedure. All of this increases their active involvement in school activities even more (Kafkoulas, 2006).

In addition, the participation has an especially positive effect for those students stuck in a disadvantageous position, providing them with new experiences since they gain a sense of «belonging» in the school community (York Consulting for the Welsh Assembly Government, 2008). All of this positively affects their psychology, in their harmonious coexistence with the other kids of the school, and their incorporation inside the school community. In addition, these kids are given the opportunity to cultivate their abilities and potential, and develop new skills that will help them satisfy their needs (Aingeal et al., 2012).

CONCLUSION

Active involvement of students in school life boosts their confidence and cultivation, and the growth of their social skills. Student participation in school, either inside the classroom, or inside the school life in general, provides the children with supplies for their future and experiences, thus making them active citizens. Problem solving, decision making, negotiations, listening to others and communicating with them, are some of the very important supplies that young students obtain. Through these procedures and the experience of participation, students gain knowledge, strategies and skills that help them express their opinion and evaluate other people's opinions. As such, by giving kids the opportunity to speak for themselves and be listened to, and by commending them, their exclusion and marginalization are decreased, and their role in school events is increased.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I have to thank my professor, Mrs. Anastasia Gkaintartzi for her valuable support, and the very good feeling of cooperation that she formed, contributing the most to the preparation of my current work.

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